

Evaluation of antimicrobial activities of crude ethyl acetate and ethanol extracts of *Morinda lucida* leaf, stem, and bark growing in Adekunle Ajasin University Botanical Garden against selected clinical isolates

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research work is to determine the antimicrobial activities of crude ethyl acetate and ethanolic extracts of *Morinda lucida* leaf, stem, and bark growing in Adekunle Ajasin University Botanical Garden against selected clinical isolates. The plant *Morinda lucida* falls under the family Rubiaceae known to have wide usage in traditional medicine. *Morinda lucida* is a tropical West African tree of medium-size about 18–25 m tall, the bark is grey to brown in color, flowers are white in color, the fruit is a drupe, seed is ellipsoid, yellowish and soft. The antibacterial potency of ethyl acetate and ethanolic extracts of *Murinda lucida* leaf, stem, and bark were tested against selected clinical isolates, the clinical isolates are *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 0157), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Salmonella typhi*, *Candida albicans* (ATCC 90029), *Klebsiella pneumonia* (ATCC 35657), *Mycobacterium fortuitum* (ATCC 6841), *Mycobacterium smegmatis* (ATCC 19420), *Mycobacterium abscessus* (ATCC 19977), *Mycobacterium phlei* (ATCC 19240), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 29213). Agar well diffusion method was used to measure the antibacterial activities of *Morinda lucida* against the clinical isolates. We observed that the, *Morinda lucida* has antimicrobial activity against the clinical isolates. It was also observed that, the ethanol extracts of leaf and bark has better antimicrobial activity compared to the ethyl acetate stem extract. But all the extracts exhibit various degrees of antimicrobial activities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Plant derived products have been used for medicinal purposes since the creation of man. Approximately about 80% of the world population today, relies on botanical preparation as medicines to meet their health needs. The problem with the botanical preparation is that most of the plants are been used indiscriminately without adequate information on associated safety and toxicity risks. Traditional medicine practice has been around for centuries and still remains very common in the developing world. It is estimated that about 80% or more of the world's population rely primarily on traditional medicine for their healthcare. Plant extracts as well as other alternative forms of

medical treatment has made large contributions to human health and well-being [12].

Morinda is a genus of flowering plants in the madder family, Rubiaceae [8]. The generic name is derived from the Latin words *morus* "mulberry", from the appearance of the fruits, and *indica*, meaning "of India" [8]. *Morinda lucida* (Rubiaceae) is a tropical West Africa rainforest tree also called Brimstone tree. In Coted'Ivoire, it is locally called Sangogo or Bondoukou alongua while in Ghana, it is known as Twi, Kon kroma or Ewe amake. Among the Togolese, the plant is popularly known as Ewe amaka or Atak ake while among the Yoruba native of South-Western Nigeria, it is called Oruwo [13].

Morinda lucida is a medicinal plant growing in many African countries and widely used as a medicine in West Africa. It is generally used as ingredients of fever teas, which are usually taken, for the traditional treatment of malaria. In West Africa *Morinda lucida* is an important plant in traditional medicine. In Nigeria, *Morinda lucida* is one of the four most used plants in the preparation of traditional medicines against fever. Decoctions and infusions or plasters of root, bark and leaves are recognized remedies against different types of fever, including yellow fever, malaria, trypanosomiasis and feverish condition during childbirth. In some cases, the plant is employed in the treatment of diabetes, hypertension, cerebral congestion, dysentery, stomach-ache, ulcers, leprosy and gonorrhea [4].

In Côte d'Ivoire a bark or leaf decoction is applied against jaundice and in DR Congo, the decoction of the stem bark or leaf is combined with a dressing of powdered root bark against itch and ringworm [1]. Akinyemi *et al.* reported in their work that the bark, root and leaf are bitter [5]. They stated that the infusion or decoction of these parts is used for the treatment of yellow fever and other forms of fever. They also reported that the decoction of the leaf is applied to the breast of women at weaning of their infants to prevent infections.

Morinda lucida is used generally for febrifuge, analgesic and laxative [27] while the decoction of the stem bark is used for the treatment of severe jaundice. As reported by [20], *Morinda lucida* is used locally in the treatment of irregular menstruation, insomnia and jaundice though did not state the parts that are useful in this purpose.

Chukwujekwu *et al.* also stated that locally, *Morinda lucida* is used in the treatment of wound infections, abscesses and chancre (The primary syphilitic ulcer associated with swelling of local lymph glands and is painless, indurated, solitary and highly infectious)[10]. Also amongst the Igede People in Benue State, Nigeria, it was reported by [31] and [15] that the decoction of the *Morinda lucida* is used twice or thrice daily as anti – diarrhea, while the leaves are used for treatment of infertility in women.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection and identification of samples

The root, leaf and stem bark from *Morinda lucida* plants were obtained in Botanical garden, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba – Akoko, Ondo state, Nigeria on the 1st of September 2015 at exactly 7:15am. The plant specimen were identified and authenticated by a botanist in the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Adekunle Ajasin University Akungba Akoko, Ondo state.

2.1.1 Preparation of extracts

The extracts were prepared from three different plant parts: the leaf, stem and bark. The plant parts were washed with distilled water, sliced and air-dried. After drying, they were powdered using a grinder. Four hundred grams of each parts were soaked in 1200 ml Ethanol and ethyl acetate in an air-tight container [5]. This was allowed to stand for 14 days to permit full extraction of the active ingredients. The fluids were then filtered using Whatman No1 filter paper. The extracts were rotary dried to obtain the concentrate. It was then kept in fridge at 4°C prior to use [21].

2.1.2 Standardization of extracts

Using aseptic condition, the extract is reconstituted by adding 1.2 g of each extract with 5 ml of dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) and 15ml of sterile distilled water making it 60mg/ml. For each extract, 7.5ml of distilled water is measured into three sterile Bijou bottle. In Bijou bottle A, 7.5 ml from 60 mg/ml extract was

added and in Bijou bottle B 2.5 ml from 60 mg/ml extract was added and Bijou bottle C 2.5 ml from Bijou bottle A was added. A is 30mg/ml, B is 15mg/ml, C is 7.5 mg/ml respectively [22-23].

2.1.3 Standardization of inoculum

Slants of the various organisms were reconstituted using an aseptic condition. Using a

sterile wire loop, approximately one isolated colony of each pure culture was transferred into 5ml of sterile nutrient broth and incubated for 24 hours. After incubation, transfer 0.1 ml of the isolated colony using a sterile needle and syringe into 9.9 ml of sterile distilled water contained in each test tube and then mixed properly. The liquid now serve as a source of inoculum containing approximately 10^6 cfu/ml of bacterial suspension [13].

2.1.4 Source of clinical isolates

The clinical isolate used for this research work were isolate from the University health center and the stock culture of the Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria. The clinical isolate used are *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 0157), *Salmonella typhi* *Candida albicans* (ATCC 900290), *Klebsiella pneumonia* (ATCC 35657), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 29213), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922). They were collected in slants in McCartney bottles containing nutrient agar and then stored in a refrigerator at -4°C [23].

2.1.5 Antimicrobial assay on *Morinda Lucida* use of agar well diffusion method

The susceptibility testing was investigated by the Agar well diffusion method. A 0.1 ml of 1:10,000 dilutions (equivalent to 10^6 cfu/ml) of fresh overnight culture of the clinical isolates grown in Muller Hinton agar and potato dextrose agar was seeded into 40 ml of Muller Hinton agar, and properly mixed in universal bottles. The mixture was aseptically poured into sterile Petri dishes and allowed to set. Using a sterile cork borer of 4 mm diameter, equidistant wells were made in the agar. Drops of the re-suspended, (2 ml per well) extracts with concentrations between 60 to 7.5 mg/ml were introduced into the wells till it was filled. Ciprofloxacin and Metronidazole 2mg/ml were used as the control experiment. The plates were allowed to stand on the bench for an hour, to allow pre-diffusion of the extracts before incubation at 37°C for 24 hours. The zones of inhibition were measured to the nearest millimeter (mm) using a standard transparent meter rule. All experiments were performed in duplicates [22-23].

3. RESULTS

The results of the research work were demonstrated and recorded in table 1-6.

Table 1 shows the effects of ethyl acetate leaf extracts of *Morinda lucida* on the selected clinical isolates. The antimicrobial activities of the plant extract ranges between 2.0 mm to

15mm zones of inhibition. It was observed that *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922) at 60mg/mL concentration has the highest zone of inhibition of 16mm and *Candida albicans* (ATCC 90029) has the lowest zone of inhibition at 15mg/mL concentration of 0.0mm zones of inhibition.

Table 2 shows the effect of ethyl acetate stem extracts *Morinda lucida* on the selected clinical isolates. The degree of antimicrobial activities ranges between 2mm to 17 mm zones of inhibition. It was observed that *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 0157) has the highest zones of inhibition of 17mm at 60 mg/mL concentration and *Candida albicans* (ATCC 90029) exhibits the lowest zone of inhibition of 0.0mm at 15mg/mL concentration.

Table 3 shows the effect of ethyl acetate bark extract of *Morinda lucida* on the clinical isolates. It was observed that the potency of antimicrobial activities ranges between 0.0 mm to 18 mm zones of inhibition. It was also observed that *Candida albicans* (ATCC 90029) has the lowest zones of inhibition of 3.0mm at 60mg/mL concentration and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (ATCC 35657) has the highest zones of inhibition of 18mm at 60mg/mL concentration.

Table 4 shows the antimicrobial activities *Morinda lucida* Ethanol stem extracts. The zones of inhibition range between 2mm and 10mm. It was observed that *Klebsiella pneumonia* (ATCC 35657) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 29213) has the lowest zones of inhibition of 0.0 mm at the 7.5 mg/ml concentrations respectively and *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 29213) has the highest zones of inhibition of 10 mm at 60 mg/ml concentration.

Table 5 shows the antimicrobial activities of *Morinda lucida* Ethanol leaf extracts. The zones of the antimicrobial activities range between 2mm and 9mm zones of inhibition and various concentrations. It was observed that *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 29213), *Salmonella typhi* and *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922) has the lowest zones of inhibition of 2.0mm at 7.5 mg/ml and 15 mg/ml concentration respectively *Candida albicans* (ATCC 90029) has the highest zones of inhibition of 10mm at 60 mg/ml concentration.

Table 6 shows the antimicrobial activities of *Morinda lucida* Ethanol bark extracts. The zones of inhibition ranges between 1.0 mm and 10.0mm zones of inhibition at various concentration. it was also observed that *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 0157) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 29213) at 7.5 mg/ml concentration has the lowest zones of inhibition of 0.0 mm and *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922) has the highest zones of inhibition of 11.0 mm at 60 mg/ml concentration.

Table 1.Effect of ethyl acetate leaf extracts of *Morinda lucida* on the clinical isolates.

Clinical Isolates	Zones of Inhibition (mm)				Ciprofloxacin 30 mg/ml	Metronidazole 30 mg/ml
	60 mg/ml	30 mg/ml	15 mg/ml	7.5 mg/ml		
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (ATCC 29213)	12.0	8.0	5.0	3.0	20.0	19.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 25922)	16.0	6.0	6.0	4.0	24.0	22.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 0157)	15.0	11.0	9.0	6.0	24.0	23.0
<i>Candida albicans</i> (ATCC 90029)	4.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	24.0	21.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> (ATCC 35657)	12.0	9.0	6.0	4.0	22.0	22.0
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	13.0	10.0	8.0	4.0	21.0	22.0

Plate 1.*Escherichia coli* seeded with *Morinda lucida* leaf extracts.**Table 2.**Effect of Ethyl Acetate Stem Extract Of *Morinda lucida* On clinical Isolates.

Clinical Isolates	Zones of Inhibition (mm)				Ciprofloxacin 30mg/ml	Metronidazole 30mg/ml
	60 mg/ml	30mg/ml	15mg/ml	7.5mg/ml		
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (ATCC 29213)	12.0	11.0	6.0	4.0	24.0	23.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 25922)	11.0	10.0	5.0	2.0	20.0	23.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 0157)	17.0	11.0	7.0	4.0	26.0	28.0
<i>Candida albicans</i> (ATCC 90029)	3.0	3.0	2.0	0.0	20.0	20.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> (ATCC 35675)	14.0	10.0	5.0	3.0	24.0	26.0
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	12.0	9.0	5.0	3.0	28.0	26.0

Plate 2. *Staphylococcus aureus* seeded with *Morinda lucida* stem extracts.

Table 3. Effect of ethyl acetate bark extracts of *Morinda lucida* on the clinical Isolates.

Clinical Isolates	Zones of Inhibition (mm)				Ciprofloxacin 30 mg/ml	Metronidazole 30 mg/ml
	60 mg/ml	30 mg/ml	15 mg/ml	7.5 mg/ml		
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (ATCC 29213)	17.0	12.0	6.0	3.0	24.0	21.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 29592)	17.0	14.0	10.0	0.0	21.0	22.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 0157)	16.0	11.0	5.0	5.0	18.0	16.0
<i>Candida albicans</i> (ATCC 90029)	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	26.0	20.0
<i>Klesiella pneumonia</i> (ATCC 35657)	18.0	12.0	8.0	0.0	28.0	27.0
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	16.0	12.0	5.0	4.0	21.0	20.0

Plate 3. *Salmonella typhi* seeded with *Morinda lucida* bark extracts.

Table 4. Antimicrobial activities of *morinda lucida* ethanolic stem extracts on clinical isolates.

Clinical Isolates	Zones of Inhibition (mm)				Ciprofloxacin 30 mg/ml	Metronidazole 30 mg/ml
	60 mg/ml	30 mg/ml	15 mg/ml	7.5 mg/ml		
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 0157)	6.0	3.0	2.0	1.0	20.0	20.0
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	7.0	4.0	3.0	2.0	19.0	20.0
<i>Candida albicans</i> (ATCC 90029)	8.0	5.0	4.0	3.0	20.0	22.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> (ATCC 35657)	5.0	4.0	2.0	0.0	28.0	20.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 25922)	9.0	7.0	4.0	3.0	20.0	22.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (ATCC 29213)	10.0	8.0	5.0	0.0	22.0	21.0

Plate 4: Plate showing zone of inhibition of *Escherichia coli* seeded with *Morinda lucida* stem extracts.**Table 5.** Antimicrobial activities of *Morinda lucida* ethanolic leaf extracts.

Clinical Isolates	Zones of Inhibition (mm)				Ciprofloxacin 30 mg/ml	Metronidazole 30 mg/ml
	60 mg/ml	30 mg/ml	15 mg/ml	7.5 mg/ml		
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 0157)	9.0	5.0	3.0	2.0	22.0	20.0
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	5.0	3.0	2.0	2.0	20.0	22.0
<i>Candida albicans</i> (ATCC 90029)	10.0	8.0	5.0	4.0	27.0	20.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> (ATCC 35657)	6.0	4.0	3.0	1.0	22.0	20.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 25922)	9.0	6.0	3.0	2.0	12.0	10.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (ATCC 29213)	8.0	5.0	3.0	0.0	14.0	11.0

Plate 4: Plates showing zone of inhibition of *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC29213) seeded with *Morinda lucida* leaf extracts.

Table 6. Antimicrobial activities of *Morinda lucida* ethanolic bark extracts

Clinical Isolates	Zones of Inhibition (mm)				Ciprofloxacin 30 mg/ml	Metronidazole 30 mg/ml
	60 mg/ml	30 mg/ml	15 mg/ml	7.5 mg/ml		
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 0157)	10.0	8.0	3.0	0.0	22.0	21.0
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	7.0	5.0	4.0	1.0	24.0	22.0
<i>Candida albicans</i> (ATCC 90029)	8.0	5.0	4.0	1.0	20.0	20.0
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> (ATCC 35657)	7.0	5.0	3.0	2.0	12.0	10.0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (ATCC 25922)	11.0	7.0	4.0	1.0	15.0	10.0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (ATCC 29213)	8.0	5.0	3.0	0.0	15.0	10.0

4. DISCUSSION

Morinda lucida family of rubiaceae is an indigenous plant found in most African countries including some parts of Nigeria such as Eastern part like Anambra State. The leaves can also be used in the treatment of fever, malaria and jaundice. The phytochemical analysis of the plant revealed the presence of some phytochemicals that are of pharmacological benefits. This research show that *Morinda lucida* leaves contain saponins, alkaloids and tannins.

Tables 1, 2 and 3, show the antimicrobial activities of ethyl acetate leaf and stem extracts. It was observed that the activity of stem extracts is higher than that of the leaf extract and the activity of bark extracts is higher than the leaf

and stem extracts on the clinical organism. it was discovered that the bark ethyl acetate extract of *Morinda lucida* has the highest inhibitory activity against all the selected clinical organism screened than both its leaf and stem. The constituent of the bark extracts connotes the reason for their antimicrobial potency. The bark extracts contain various degrees of phytochemicals and antioxidant like flavonoids, steroids and phenols just to mention a few. This phytochemical and antioxidant dictates the antimicrobial activity of this plant extracts. They both function in the removal of free radical in the human system which shows their efficacy on all clinical isolates especially the clinical isolates under this research work. The presence of phytochemical like alkaloids explain why the leaves can be used in the treatment of

headache, malaria and other forms of fever, while the presence of tannin explains why it is used in the treatment of diarrhea [2,3,18].

Tables 4, 5 and 6 show the effect of ethanol extracts of leaf stem and bark. It was also observed that both the stem and the bark exhibit the highest zones of inhibition compares to the extracts of leaf. It was discovered that ethanol extract of *Morinda lucida* bark has the highest inhibitory activities which correlates with research of [15]. The antimicrobial activity of many plant extract has been previously reviewed and classified as strong, medium or weak [19,26,32] have shown that *Morinda lucida* had strong and consistent inhibitory effects against various bacterial. Earlier studies though, have reported better antimicrobial activity for *Morinda lucida* [21].

Several investigation had reported that *Morinda lucida* and other medicinal plants contains antimicrobial substances [6,17,31]. The results of this present study agree with the reports of these previous scientists, who showed wide range of some active plant substances against certain organisms. Plant extracts have been used for many thousands of years in food preservation (29), pharmaceuticals, alternative medicine and natural therapies [16,25]. It is necessary to investigate those plants scientifically which have been used in traditional medicine to improve the quality of healthcare. Plant extracts are potential sources of novel antimicrobial compounds [8] especially against *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 (17) *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213, *Candida albicans* ATCC 90029, *Klebsiella pneumonia* ATCC 35657, and *Salmonella typhi* [2,3,17].

In general, the levels of medicinal plants and their compounds necessary to inhibit microbial growth are higher in foods than in culture media. This is due to interactions between phenolic compounds and the food matrix [17,22,23] and should be considered for commercial applications. The plant extracts, presented positive antimicrobial activity for *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 (17) *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213, *Candida albicans* ATCC 90029, *Klebsiella pneumonia* ATCC 35657, and *Salmonella typhi* [2,3,17] as shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4. Antimicrobial properties of plants are desirable tools in the control of undesirable microorganisms especially in the treatment of infectious diseases as shown in Tables 2,3 and 4 which correlates with previous research of [3,27]. The active components usually interfere with growth and metabolism of microorganisms in a negative manner [13]. Evaluating plants from the traditional African system of medicine provides us with clues as to how these plants can be used in the treatment of diseases and the use of this plant in formulating various antibiotic and in discovery of drug in herbal preparation which must be encourage in all ramification of life.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, these research finding has been able to lend further credence to the ethnobotanical potentials of *Morinda lucida* especially in the rural communities where orthodox medicine are unavailable and in the promotion of phytomedicine. It is observed that *Morinda lucida* inhibited the in vitro growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* (ATCC 35657) and other clinical isolate during the course of this research work Thus, they can be used in the treatment of infectious diseases caused by these resistant microbes. The study also validates the significance of *Morinda lucida* as a valuable source of new leads for drug development. It is possible to state that the *Morinda lucida* plant bear antimicrobial activity. Comparisons with pertinent data from literature indicate that, according to the methodology adopted in studies on antimicrobial activity, However, the extracts are additional answer to man's quest to its health problems showing that mostly all the plants parts possesses a lot of potential as an additional source of antibacterial substances to fight against or inhibit the medicinally important pathogens that has been eminent among man over the years.

It is thereby recommended that the medicinal plant such as *Morinda lucida* and other types of medicinal plants should be studied and exploited for use.

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